

Toward chiral polyamidoamine (PAMAM) dendritic architecture with tartaric acid core

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Manuscript received 26 June 2001, revised 7 September 2001, accepted 25 September 2001

A convenient approach to the synthesis of new chiral hybrid poly(amidoamine) (PAMAM) dendrimers has been reported. Diethyl L-tartrate is converted into its amine functionalized derivative **1**, which serves as the initiator core for the construction of the chiral, monodispersed PAMAM-type tartaric acid centered hybrid dendrimers **2** and **3**.

Dendrimers have become a subject of intense research¹ in recent years due to their unique structures and properties². Of these chiral dendritic macromolecules³ have been the subject of keen interest because these offer the prospect of novel materials for chiral recognition and enantioselective binding of small chiral guest molecules, leading to the possible applications in chemical separations, sensor technology, and asymmetric catalysis. On the other hand, polyamidoamine (PAMAM) dendrimers are also of current interest because of their novel structural properties and attractive potential applications in a variety of fields⁴. In this context, a challenging target is the construction of well-defined PAMAM dendrimer possessing chiral core unit.

We report herein for the first time the successful synthesis and characterization of optically active, monodisperse PAMAM dendrimers **2** and **3** (Scheme 1) exploiting the utilization of diethyl L-tartrate as the chiral core unit.

Results and Discussion

The divergent approach, pioneered by Tomalia *et al.*⁵, has been employed for the synthesis of chiral PAMAM dendrimer **3** of generation upto 1.5. Tartaric acid core is especially appealing for the design of dendrimers due to its easy availability from the chiral pool and renewable resources, biocompatibility, low toxicity and natural polyfunctionality. In addition, intrinsic chirality may be introduced into the dendrimer by using tartaric acid core. The structures of **2** and **3** were unequivocally characterized by means of NMR, IR and fast atom bombardment (FAB) mass spectroscopy.

IR spectra of **2** and **3** display the characteristic ester C=O stretching at 1708 and 1725 cm⁻¹ respectively. The amide-I stretching of both these dendritic systems appears at 1640 and 1627 cm⁻¹, respectively, whereas the peaks at 1620 cm⁻¹ for both these systems are due to N-H bending of the

amide group: ¹H NMR spectra of both **2** and **3** show a peak at δ 3.62 and 5.70, respectively, corresponding to the methine protons of L-tartaric acid unit. The characteristic peak due

Scheme 1. (i) Ethylenediamine (30 equiv.), EtOH, room temperature (RT), 5 days, (ii) methylacrylate (10 equiv.), MeOH, RT, 3 days, (iii) ethylenediamine (80 equiv.), MeOH, RT, 5 days, (iv) methyl acrylate (20 equiv.), MeOH, RT, 3 days.

to ester methyl protons appears at δ 3.56 and 3.60, respectively. The peak assignable to the methylene protons appears at δ 3.45–2.21. These findings are also confirmed by ¹³C NMR spectral data for **3**. The FAB-MS spectrum of **3** shows the parent ion peak (C₆₀H₁₀₆N₁₂O₂₄) at *m/z* 1370 which is almost consistent with the calculated value. The specific rotation value of these dendrimers decreases with increasing generation number, in agreement with the observations made in the literature⁶.

In summary, we have thus elaborated a practical method for the facile and uniform synthesis of chiral PAMAM dendrimers without carrying out protection-deprotection chemistry. The methodology is experimentally straightforward and utilizes the divergent approach, pioneered by Tomalia. This new hybrid dendrimers may offer some possible advantageous properties compared to classical PAMAMs, such as altered overall shape, better biodegradability, lower toxicity and chirality. We anticipate that chiral dendrimers of this type will have applications in chiral sensory systems. Further studies in our laboratory are in progress.

Experimental

IR spectra (KBr) were recorded with a Shimadzu CO IR-470 spectrophotometer, NMR spectra (DMSO- d_6) on Bruker AM200 and UNITY-400 'unityultra' spectrometers and mass spectrum (glycerol) in continuum FB⁺ scan mode by using VG Quattro Triple quadrupole probe. Specific rotation was recorded with a Jasco-DIP-370 polarimeter using 1% aqueous sucrose solution as the standard.

Synthesis : Diethyl L-tartrate was treated with excess of ethylenediamine (1 : 30 mole ratio) to get amine functionalized derivative **1** which served as initiator core for the development of PAMAM generations. The tartatic acid derivative **1** represents a stereochemically well-defined, oligofunctional molecule with two uniformly functionalized spacers. Compound **1** was then submitted to the reaction sequence leading to PAMAM dendrimer generation **2** consisting of the exhaustive Michael addition of the amine functionalized core to methyl acrylate. Amidation of the resulting methyl esters of **2** with ethylenediamine followed by Michael addition step led to the chiral PAMAM dendrimer **3** in quantitative yield : dendrimer **2** honey coloured gummy liq., ν_{\max} 3312 (OH, NH), 1708 (ester C=O), 1640 (amide-I), 1620 (amide-II), 1385, 1208 cm^{-1} (-CO-O-C); ^1H NMR (200 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 8.0–7.5 (2H, s, CONH), 4.5 (b s, OH), 3.62 (2H, s, CH(OH)), 3.56 (12H, s, CO₂CH₃), 3.47 (4H, m, CONHCH₂), 2.98–3.15 (12H, m,

NCH₂CH₂CO₂CH₃, NCH₂CH₂NHCO), 2.30–2.69 (8H, m, all other CH₂); $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{20} = +64.28^\circ$ (c 0.0014 g/ml, H₂O); dendrimer **3** (G1.5), honey coloured gummy liq.; FAB-MS m/z calcd. 1363, found 1370 (M+1); ν_{\max} 3453, 3231 (OH, NH), 2967, 2922 (CH), 1725 (ester C=O), 1627 (amide-I), 1620 (amide-II), 1406, 1344, 1200, 1059 (-CO-O-C), 974, 813 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (400 MHz; DMSO- d_6) δ 8.2–7.6 (b s, CONH), 5.70 (2H, s, CH(OH)-), 4.50 (2H, b s, OH), 3.60 (24H, s, CO₂CH₃), 3.41 (12H, m, CONHCH₂), 3.10–2.80 (36H, m, 4NCH₂-CH₂CONH, 8NCH₂CH₂CO₂CH₃, 6NCH₂CH₂NHCO), 2.80–2.21 (24H, m, all other CH₂); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 170.0 (NC=O; out), 167.5 (NC=O, in), 166.25 (C=O), 70.0, 59.8, 50.4, 47.8, 46.5, 43.9, 41.3, 31.25, 28.75, 27.50; $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{20} = +34.44^\circ$ (c 0.0018 g/ml, H₂O).

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